

From Vibes to Waifus: Why Indonesians Love Their Coffee Shops

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Abstract

The rapid growth of modern coffee shops in Indonesia has transformed these establishments into prominent “third places” for Gen Z and Gen Y audience, functioning as a space for social interaction, work activities, and a form of lifestyle expression in this era. Nevertheless, the increase market saturation within the coffee shops industry has seen to be intensified due to the competitive pressures, compelling café shop brands to adopt innovative marketing strategies, including the use of character collaborations incorporation with anime trends. In alignment with SDG 8 on Decent Work and Economic Growth, the present study aims to examine the effects of character collaboration, with buyer interest serving as a mediating variable in the Indonesian coffee shop industry. By implementing a quantitative approach, utilizing the Stimulus–Organism–Response (S-O-R) framework and the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) to further analyze the relationships between the independent variables (character collaboration, place ambience, and anime trends), the mediating variable (buyer interest), and the dependent variable (purchase intention) among coffee shop consumers in Indonesia.

Keyword: Indonesia coffee shop industry, Purchase intention, Buyer interest, Character collaboration, Place ambience, Anime trends, Gen Z, Gen Y, SDG 8

1. Introduction

Accompanying this shift has been an explosive growth in the number of modern coffee shops, marking a significant change in the coffee consumer experience. Through their inviting environment and extensive beverage menus, these shops draw large crowds not only as places for social and business interactions, but also as multipurpose modern venues. In addition, they provide alternative workplaces for students, young employees, and freelancers, which strengthens urban coffee consumption and culture (Coffee Market Trends: Expert Insights [2025], n.d; Purwanto, 2025). The coffee shop sector in Indonesia itself has expanded quickly over the last ten years, becoming a “third place” for urban workers and young people to work, study, and socialize. According to an article from GoodStats (2024), several surveys mentioned that 27% of respondents said they attend coffee shops one or two times a week, indicating that these places have become a popular destination for people in the 18-24 age range. This emphasizes coffee shops as more than just locations to get coffee; they are sociable and productive places that support a lifestyle choice.

However, despite this expansion, the industry is also beginning to show signs of saturation, indicating that the number of coffee shops and cafes has skyrocketed in recent years, resulting in more intense rivalry and demanding more innovative marketing tactics. These were supported both domestically and internationally, as it is anticipated that at-home coffee consumption, measured by retail sales in supermarkets and convenience stores, will bring in around US\$96.45 billion by 2025 (Statista,2025). Out-of-home consumption at cafés, restaurants, and bars is anticipated to generate US\$376.70 billion during that time, for a total estimated market value of US\$473.10 billion. Furthermore, the market is expected to continue growing, with domestic revenues expected to increase between 2025 and 2029 at a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 2.96%. Numerous businesses are entering the coffee industry in response to persistently high demand signals, which are strengthening the perception of a “crowded market” and expanding customer options, both of which are indicators of retail market saturation (Xiao, 2024).

Coffee shops' biggest challenge is not just to maintain competitive prices and high-quality products, but also to differentiate themselves in a way that appeals to Gen Z and Y consumers and their attachment to

pop culture. The purchasing decisions of Gen Y are typically based on social influence and self-representation, which are reinforced by extensive information searching. Meanwhile, on the other hand, Gen Z has been influenced by the quick development of technology, and is less brand loyal but more flexible to changes. Both generations are further compelled by modernization to modify their consumption habits in response to the current trends (Yanti Nasution & Kurnia, 2021). Companies nowadays are starting to adopt product innovation and character collaboration to generate buzz, grow their audience, and encourage buying. Character collaboration with a specific brand is positioned in marketing literature as a strategy for differentiation, innovation, and attracting new consumers in the Gen Z market, which aligns with this approach. The ambience of the location is a significant aspect, in addition to collaboration (Pengmao, 2025).

According to other findings from a [GoodStats survey](#) mentioned that 84% of Gen Z and Gen Y customers are more influenced by the location's atmosphere (ambience) when selecting a coffee shop, compared to other criteria like promotion and discounts, which were selected by only 37% of respondents. Ambience, such as store interior design, store exterior design, store layout, and interior display, affects customer impressions of quality and loyalty (Budiman & Dananjoyo, 2021). Research on coffee shops demonstrated that a welcoming environment not only increases customer satisfaction, but also fortifies the desire to return and make a purchase (Handayani et al., 2022). However, on the ground observations shows that several well-known coffee shops are implementing collaboration-based promotional techniques, such as introducing limited-edition menus or selling products in alliances with other business sectors (anime or any character brands). This leads to a gap between the marketing tactics used by coffee shops (collaborative promotion) and the preferences expressed by customers (comfort as priority). In instance, well known coffee shops in Indonesia, such as TOMORO Coffees' have done collaboration with Jujutsu Kaisen and Genshin Impact, and another collaboration between Kopi Kenangan with One Piece, which connected joint menu items and limited-edition packaging. The phenomenon of collaboration cafes is also growing in Asia, where anime collaboration cafes are proving to be a successful means of turning fandom into visitation and purchase behavior.

Therefore, this study uses the Stimulus-Organism-Response (S-O-R) paradigm to investigate how character collaboration, place ambience, and anime trends affect purchase intention through buyer interest (mediator). The goal of this study is to add to the body of knowledge on purchase intention in the food and beverage industry, especially the coffee shop sector, by presenting buyer interest as a psychological mechanism that connects environmental stimuli with consumer behavioral reactions. Additionally, this study also relies on the use of the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) to access how buyer interest is affected by character collaboration, place ambience, and anime trends in influencing purchase intention, which expected to provide practical contributions in forms of strategic insights for coffee shop industry players in Indonesia in designing marketing strategic that align with consumer preferences in an increasingly competitive market

2. Literature Review

This study adopts the SOR paradigm as one of the main conceptual frameworks for understanding consumer behavior that suggests that the feelings or internal behavior of a human (object/organism) are caused by the external environment (stimuli) (Mehrabian & Russell as stated in Hochreiter et al., 2023). The processing on these internal stimuli can be conscious or unconscious, including the perception and interpretation of the environment that influences a person's feelings and decisions. **Stimuli** function as both internal and external information, affecting an individual's behaviors, decisions, and buying habits. **Object/Organism** serves as an input that supplies cognitive and activating frameworks, which facilitate the creation of a product and a set of decision awareness. **Reaction/Response**, conversely, represents a stage of conscious information processing that signifies the onset of the true decision-making process, subsequently initiating the reaction phase. When it comes to coffee shops, the atmosphere of the place is a significant factor as it is typically treated as a part of the overall environment (Budiman & Dananjoyo, 2021). In the area of atmosphere response, emotional states brought about by the atmosphere and the environment are then transformed into behaviors, which are expressed as purchase intention (Humairoh et al., 2023). Aligning with the S-O-R paradigm, store ambience is a stimulus that leads to positive emotions, comfort and curiosity

(organism), which then results in response outcomes like greater purchase intentions and willingness to spend time in a store. The ambience of the place in the S-O-R strategy can be seen as one of the factors in the strategy of the coffee shop, which is beyond the functional product to increase consumer attraction. Hence, purchase intention can be seen as the fundamental response to the ambience (Siregar, 2025).

Another theory adopted in this study having been introduced in 1991 Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) by Ajzen, as it discusses three primary elements that shape individual intention toward behavioral engagement, which are **attitude toward the behavior, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control**. This theory is used to examine Indonesia's highly saturated coffee shop market, where many businesses now use character collaboration and the growing anime trend as fresh attraction to stand out and differentiate themselves in the eyes of the younger consumers. The concept of character collaboration also reflects on how positively customers attitude towards a certain behavior, shaped by their beliefs about the expected outcomes. Another study also suggests that consumer attitudes result from favorable assessments of the product's associated symbolic and emotional values (Supriadi et al., n.d.). Therefore, collaborating popular character within the industry can boost recognition through the emotional bonds consumers form with specific characters, strengthening the urge to buy the product (Tae JANG et al., 2024). Subjective norm illustrates on how social pressure and group expectation shape buying intentions. Peer and online community influences significantly impact the consumption behavior (Arli et al., 2015). Thus, when coffee shops collaborate with notable characters, consumers feel the urge to do so to satisfy the community norms. Meanwhile, perceived behavioral control relates to how restricted consumers feel when undertaking certain behaviors. A study from Malaysia implies that perceived control over product availability was directly related to the intention to purchase, particularly for phenomenon-based products (Lim & Ting, 2012). Subsequently, TPB describes purchase disposition as well as opens avenues to analyze how character collaborations get assimilated into the decision-making process at the level of the consumer.

Despite the growing interest in this marketing strategy, there remains limited empirical evidence on how character collaborations influence purchase intention in the F&B sector, especially within the Indonesia's coffee shop industry and the consumption culture within the younger generation. While the TPB framework tends to concentrate on the individual psychological aspects of the purchase intention, the present study adopts the Consumer Culture Theory (CCT) by Arnould and Thompson in 2005 to offer an alternative angle of consumption as an act of symbolically and interwoven process within social and cultural frameworks. Unlike traditional consumption market, the loyalty for a brand is often manifested as emotional dependence and cultural identification on the brand, hence exceeding the simple purchasing behavior (Y. Chen, 2025). The CCT framework can be used within the context of anime trends in Indonesia to analyze why character collaboration in the coffee shop industry can capture more consumers. A study by Shi Yichun (2024) also explains on how anime is a form of escapism that can be reflected in consumption behavior, psychograph, and characteristics in a stronger form. Not only that, they can also share their shopping experience to further strengthened their connection with the society (Shi, 2024). This suggest that anime trends are no longer confined to simple forms of entertainment but are now an integral part of the daily lives of youths globally. Coffee shops in Indonesia, especially that utilize anime inside a character collaboration differentiate themselves from competitors and capitalize on popular culture, thus it extends beyond marketing strategies and fosters cultural engagement to influence consumer behavior.

The character collaboration has emerged as an integrated marketing strategy in the F&B industry to attract younger audiences, especially Gen Z and Gen Y (Tae JANG et al., 2024). One case in point is the use characters, especially anime character that are culturally significantly symbols that further heighten consumer-brand interaction by their appeal, emotional connection, and the character value where consumer-character attachment and product congruence are proven to positively influence intention to purchase (C. Y. Chen et al., 2022; Hussain et al., 2020; Prof. Parul Khanna et al., 2024; Tae JANG et al., 2024). Therefore, this research came up with the hypothesis:

H1: Character Collaboration has a significant positive effect on Buyer Interest.

Geared through the S-O-R paradigm by Mehrabian and Russell in 1974, the ambience of a coffee shop is instrumental to the consumer's decision to purchase, as well as to the assessment and emotional processing the customer engages in before the purchase. The ambience is further defined along three interrelated dimensions: ambient setting, like music tempo, lighting, and pleasant scent (Kim & Moon, 2009, as cited in Budiman & Dananjoyo, 2021; Nusairat et al., 2020), configuration of the spatial layout and design, serving functional & aesthetic principles, and the social servicescape. According to recent research on coffee shops, maintaining customer interest and loyalty requires friendly staff and reasonable crowding levels (Humairoh et al., 2023). When taken as a whole, these aspects show how place ambience works as a multifaceted construct that greatly influences the interaction between consumers' interest and purchase intention. Therefore, this research came up with the hypothesis:

H2: Place Ambience has a significant positive effect on Buyer Interest.

H3: Place Ambience has a significant direct effect on Purchase Intention.

Through strategic advertisement filled with anime aesthetics, brands freshly harness the niche of anime and leave a lasting impression as 'one of a kind' (Klebanskaja & Andriukhanova, 2018). The anime driven engagement enables the likelihood of making a purchase by several factor, including the popularity, emotional engagement, as well as trend driven consumption. This was further supported by research that finds similar results in which, purchasing intention for anime-collaboration product would rise due to emotional bonding between the consumer and the product itself ((Durmaz et al., 2022; Fahlevi & Aidnilla Sinambela, 2024; Louati et al., 2025). Therefore, this research came up with the hypothesis:

H4: Anime Trend has a significant positive effect on Buyer Interest.

Interest from a buyer's perspective and its cognitive, affective, and conative aspects work as a mediator on buyer's purchase intentions. Cognitive interest refers to a degree of awareness and overall knowledge a consumer has towards a particular stimulus, and how product understanding can increase the likelihood of purchasing a product. This positive experience sure can motivate customers to make a continuous transaction on a daily basis (Santoso et al., 2022). Affective interest involves an emotional engagement and encompasses the elements of enjoyment, arousal, and trust, which can shift attention from negative to neutral and the two positives, leading to stronger purchase intention (Bleir et al., 2019 as cited in Santoso et al., 2022; Zhou & Baskaran, 2025). Conative interest illustrates the readiness and willingness to purchase, revisit, and pay premium prices, which emerge when the cognitive and affective elements cohere and drive purchase behaviors (Park et al., 2008; Su et al., 2019). Collectively, these dimensions of buyer interest demonstrate and serve as a psychological function between stimulus and consumer behavior, which in turn facilitates their purchase intentions. Therefore, this research came up with the hypothesis:

H5: Buyer Interest has a significant positive effect on Purchase Intention.

3. Research Model Framework

The proposed research model seeks to empirically assess the role of character collaboration, place ambience, and anime trend in influencing purchase intention, with buyers' interest as a mediating variable. In this model, place ambience is assumed to have a direct impact on purchase intention as well as an indirect impact through the buyer's interest. On the other hand, character collaboration and anime trends are proposed to have an indirect impact on purchase intention through the buyer's interest as a mediator. Thus, the model embodies a causal configuration empirically substantiated in other theories and studies, elucidating the psychological interest that mediates the external marketing stimuli and purchase behavior of consumers.

The hypotheses of this study are as followed:

- H1:** Character Collaboration has a significant positive effect on Buyer Interest.
- H2:** Place Ambience has a significant positive effect on Buyer Interest.
- H3:** Place Ambience has a significant direct effect on Purchase Intention.
- H4:** Anime Trend has a significant positive effect on Buyer Interest.
- H5:** Buyer Interest has a significant positive effect on Purchase Intention.

4. Research Methods

4.1 Research Design

This study adopts a quantitative approach with an explanatory approach to test the hypotheses and examine the correlational relationships between the variables. The quantitative approach itself is a research method that aims to measure and analyze phenomena systematically with the help of statistics to obtain objective and measurable findings. In this case, the primary objective of this study is to analyze how the influence of character collaboration, place ambience, and anime trends (independent variables) affects purchase intention (dependent variable) through buyer interest (mediator).

4.2 Data Sampling

The present study uses purposive sampling method to analyze the data in which not all members on the general population has the characteristics related to this study's focus. The population of this study consisted of Generation Z (born in 1997-2012) and Generation Y (born in 1981-1996) living in the Greater Jakarta (Jabodetabek), that have visited and made any purchases in Indonesia's coffee shops. According to (Hair et al., 2019). guideline for Structural Equation Modeling (SEM), which recommends the 5 to 10-times rule. Therefore, with the 15 indicators, the minimum sample needed was 75 respondents. Meanwhile, this study exceeds with a total sample size of 115 respondents with all data eligible to be retained for the final analysis.

4.3 Measurement

The research instrument used in this study was a structured questionnaire consisting of 23 questions, which were compiled based on several main constructs in the model framework of the study. This questionnaire was compiled using Indonesian language to facilitate completion by Generation Z and Y in Indonesia. Each question in the questionnaire was measured using a 5-point Likert scale, range between 1 indicated as "Strongly Disagree" to 5 indicated as "Strongly Agree". The validity and reliability of the instrument were tested and all constructs showed a Cronbach's alpha > 0.70, indicating good reliability. The variables measured in this study include character collaboration, place ambience, and anime trends (independent variables), purchase intention (dependent variable) and buyer interest (mediator).

Variables	Operational Definition	Indicators	Adaptive Statement
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<p>Character Collaboration (C. Y. Chen et al., 2022; Hussain et al., 2020; Prof. Parul Khanna et al., 2024; Tae JANG et al., 2024)</p>	<p>By using fictional characters of all type, especially digital ones, captures attention easily and gain popularity. The way they are portrayed give a sense of emotional connection (bonding) to increase a likelihood of a purchase to be made.</p>	Character Appeal	<p>CCA1. I am more interested in a product when the coffeeshop I visit uses famous characters or the ones that I like.</p>
		Emotional Connection	<p>CCA2. I am more interested in products from coffee shops that collaborate with famous characters or characters that I like, because such collaborations evoke nostalgia and emotional closeness.</p>
		Character Value	<p>CCA3. I am more interested in a product from a coffee shop that is collaborating with a famous character or one that I like, because it makes the product seem more valuable to me.</p>
<p>Place Ambience (Budiman & Dananjoyo, 2021; Humairoh et al., 2023; Muhamad Kautsar et al., 2025; Siregar, 2025)</p>	<p>When it comes to coffee shops, the atmosphere of the place is a significant factor and overall environment, including the interior and exterior design, layout arrangement and the service offered by the shop. The comfort offered by the place can impact the willingness and satisfaction for customer to make a purchase.</p>	Ambient Setting	<p>PAB1. The effects of the music, lighting, cleanliness, and aroma at the coffee shop I visited influenced how long I spent there.</p>
		Spatial Layout and Design	<p>PAB2. The seating layout, interior design, and decor of a coffee shop I visit influence how long I spend there.</p>
		Social Servicescape	<p>PAB3. Interaction with the staff at the coffee shop I visit affects how long I spend there.</p>
<p>Anime Trend (Durmaz et al., 2022; Fahlevi & Aidnilla Sinambela, 2024; Louati et al., 2025; Shi, 2024)</p>	<p>The trend describes a situation when people make a purchase, primarily based on the popularity of the product. In the context of popularity, the use of anime characters connects an emotional experience through narrative stories influence the customer especially the one watching the show.</p>	Popularity	<p>ATD1. Coffee shop products will look more attractive and valuable when they follow popular trends, such as the current hype surrounding anime.</p>
		Emotional Engagement	<p>ATD2. I was drawn to a product at a coffee shop during an anime collaboration because it brought back memories and emotional ties to the anime story.</p>
		Trend-Driven Consumption	<p>ATD3. My interest in a coffee shop product is</p>

			more influenced by trends, such as collaborations with popular anime, than by the product's functionality for me.
Buyer's Interest (Lim & Ting, 2012; Park et al., 2008; Zhou & Baskaran, 2025)	The positive purchase experience that strengthens consumers' evaluation and reduces uncertainty, while emotional response enhances favorable attachment and attitudes toward a product. The consumer's final behavioral response driven by both cognitive and emotional engagement represent the intention for someone to make a purchase.	Cognitive Interest	BIN1. When I am interested in a product at a coffee shop, I always consider it seriously before deciding to visit that coffee shop.
		Affective Interest	BIN2. Having positive feelings (such as happiness, trust, or liking) towards the products at a coffee shop makes me more interested in those products.
		Conative Interest	BIN3. My interest in a coffee shop's products depends on the price I have to pay for them.
Purchase Intention (Kripesh et al., 2020; Muhammad naufal atiyah & Fiska Kusumawati, 2023; Wang et al., 2023; Zare et al., 2024)	A consumer's strong desire or intention to purchase a particular product or service in the future, which arises after going through various stages of information processing and attitude towards the product.	Product Usefulness	PIN1. When I visit a coffee shop, I feel that the products available provide benefits that suit my needs, which encourages me to buy them.
		Opinion (Perception)	PIN2. My opinion about the quality of a coffee shop influences my intention to buy there. If I rate the coffee shop positively, I will be more interested in buying its products.
		Behavioral Control	PIN3. I have complete control over my resources (money, time, and access), so the decision to buy drinks at a coffee shop is entirely up to me.

Table 1. Operational Definition Table

4.4 Data Collection

The data collecting was conducted through distributing online questionnaire via Google Forms, and shared on multiple social networks (e.g., Line, WhatsApp, Instagram, Twitter/X, Telegram), addressing Generation Z or Generation Y (Millennial) respondents in the Greater Jakarta (Jabodetabek), specifically those who have visited and made any purchases in Indonesian coffee shops. The data collection lasted

approximately two months period. The questionnaire contained screening questions to ensure respondent that filled the form has visit/purchased product from the coffee shops before ensuring the respondents meet the demographic criteria and proceeding with the main survey items. This method ensures that the data gathered suitable for the targeted population in this study.

4.5 Data Analysis

By using Structural Equation Modeling - Partial Least Squares (SEM-PLS) with SmartPLS 4.0 software, the collected data was analyzed and further conducted in two main stages to answer the research objectives:

a) Measurement Model (Outer Model) Evaluation

To make sure that the present research indicators and construct are both valid and reliable, the convergent validity was evaluated using outer loadings greater than (> 0.708) and the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) valued above (> 0.50). The discriminant validity was examined through cross-loadings (with Fornell-Larcker criterion), and ensuring the HTMT values were lower than 0.90. Construct reliability was verified using Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability, with both expected to exceed 0.70.

b) Structural Model (Inner Model) Evaluation

Evaluating the proposed hypotheses in the present research, the analysis assessed the model's explanatory strength using the Coefficient of Determination (R^2) and then examined the significance of the Path Coefficients through bootstrapping with 5000 subsamples. The significance was determined based on T-statistics greater than 1.96 and p-values below 0.05. This approach directly addressed the research objectives regarding the impact of Character Collaboration (H1), Place Ambience on Buyer Interest (H2), Place Ambience direct effect on Purchase Intention (H3), Anime trend (H4), as well as the mediating effect of Buyer Interest on Purchase Intention (H5).

5. Findings

5.1 Respondents Profile

The present research collected data from 115 valid respondents who met the criteria of Generation Z or Generation Y (Millennial) respondents in the Greater Jakarta (Jabodetabek), specifically those who have visited and made any purchases in Indonesian coffee shops. The tables below summarize the demographic and purchase behavioral characteristics of the respondents.

Table 2. Demographic Characteristics

Demographic Profile	Characteristic
Gender	Most respondents are female (54%), followed by male respondents (46%).
Age	Most respondents aged between 17-35 years (73%), followed by those aged between 36-45 years (19%), above 45 years (6%), and below 17 years (2%).
Area of Living	Most respondents live in Jakarta (47%), followed by Tangerang (21%), Bekasi and Bogor (10%), Depok (10%), Surabaya (1%), and Manado (1%).
Occupation	Most respondents are business owner and private-sector employees (68%), followed by students (29%), and unemployed (4%).
Whether they have visited and made any purchases in Indonesian coffee shops	A total of 115 respondents (100%) has visited and made any purchases in Indonesian coffee shops

Table 3. Purchase Behavior Characteristic

Purchase Behavior	Characteristic
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Reasons of Purchase	Most respondents valued taste (69%), followed by price (68%), strategic location (46%), place ambience (39%), promotion with character collaboration (34%), and wifi availability (31%).
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5.2 Measurement Model Evaluation Results

5.2.1 Convergent Validity and Outer Loadings

Convergent validity assesses whether indicator adequately measure their intended construct. A construct achieves convergent validity when the outer loadings exceed 0.708 and the AVE is more than 0.50, which indicates that the construct explain more than 50% of the variance of its indicators (Hair et al., 2019). After refining the sample data, it shows that all the indicators retained in the model met the loading threshold, and achieved an all-constructs AVE values ≥ 0.50 . All the variables construct retained fifteen indicators with loadings exceed 0.708 (**Table 4**). The results indicate that all remaining indicators have strong explanatory power toward their latent constructs.

Table 4. Convergent Validity (AVE)

Variable	AVE
Anime Trend	0.886
Buyer Interest	0.775
Character Collaboration	0.911
Place Ambience	0.777
Purchase Intention	0.793

5.2.2 Discriminant Validity (HTMT)

Discriminant validity makes sure that each construct is truly distinct and not overlapping with each other. The present study used Heterotrait–Monotrait Ratio (HTMT) to assess the five latent variables in the model (**Table 5**). The result indicates that most construct pairs demonstrate acceptable discriminant validity, with HTMT values remaining below the recommended threshold of 0.85. However, two construct pairs exceeded the threshold, signaling discriminant validity concerns.

Table 5. Discriminant Validity (HTMT)

	Anime Trend	Buyer Interest	Character Collaboration	Place Ambience	Purchase Intention
Anime Trend	0.941				
Buyer Interest	0.692	0.881			
Character Collaboration	0.892	0.660	0.954		
Place Ambience	0.509	0.784	0.460	0.882	
Purchase Intention	0.577	0.867	0.585	0.804	0.891

5.2.3 Construct Reliability

Construct reliability was assessed using Composite Reliability (CR) and Cronbach's Alpha (CA), applying a minimum threshold of 0.70. As indicated in **Table 6**, every construct recorded values exceeding the benchmark, confirming satisfactory reliability across the model.

Table 6. Construct Reliability

Variable	Composite Reliability	Cronbach's Alpha
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Anime Trend	0.959	0.936
Buyer Interest	0.912	0.855
Character Collaboration	0.968	0.951
Place Ambience	0.913	0.855
Purchase Intention	0.920	0.869

5.3 Structural Model (Inner Model) Evaluation Results

The hypothesis testing via a path coefficient analysis has confirmed the significance of findings in Table 7. Results show that Character Collaboration does not significantly impact Buyer Interest, therefore H1 is not supported; however, Place Ambience has a strong and significant positive impact on Buyer Interest, supporting H2, and also has a significant positive impact on Purchase Intention, thus supporting H3. The results also indicate that there was no evidence of an impact of Anime Trend on Buyer Interest; therefore, H4 is not supported.

Lastly, there is a strong positive correlation between Buyer Interest and Purchase Intention (H5 supported). In summary, this study shows the importance of both Place Ambience and Buyer Interest in predicting Purchase Intentions, as neither Character Collaboration nor Anime Trend impacts either of them directly.

Table 7. Path Coefficients and Hypothesis Testing

Correlation	Hypothesis	Original Sample (β)	T-Statistics	P-Values	Desc
Character Collaboration → Buyer Interest	H1	0.192	1.244	0.214	Reject
Place Ambience → Buyer Interest	H2	0.582	9.183	0.000	Accept
Place Ambience → Purchase Intention	H3	0.322	3.810	0.000	Accept
Anime Trend → Buyer Interest	H4	0.225	1.558	0.120	Reject
Buyer Interest → Purchase Intention	H5	0.615	7.282	0.000	Accept

6. Discussion

6.1 The Effect of Character Collaboration on Buyer Interest

The findings reveal that Character Collaboration does not appear to be statistically significant to Buyer Interest ($\beta = 0.192$, $p = 0.214$). This doesn't align with the past research by Tae JANG et al., 2024, which mentions that the creative combination of character popularity and product plays an important role in attracting consumers' attention in the F&B industry in Indonesia's coffee shop.

The differences found in these findings may stem from Gen Z and Gen Y audiences of Jabodetabek in general, who do not view character collaborations as a key factor in their purchasing decisions, particularly regarding the use of such collaborations in Indonesia's coffee shop promotional strategies. The results suggest that in general, the promotional strategies of character collaboration don't fully influence their interest in buying the products. Hence, the character collaboration can be ineffective when aimed at consumers who are unfamiliar with the featured collaborative characters.

6.2 The Direct and Indirect Effect of Place Ambience on Purchase Intention

The indirect effect of Place Ambience confirms to reveal a strong and significant positive relationship with Buyer Interest as the mediator ($\beta = 0.582$, $p < 0.001$). This finding aligns with previous

research by Budiman & Dananjoyo, 2021, mentioning that coffee shops atmosphere deemed to be useful in attracting consumer attention, by creating a unique and viral atmosphere can be done to increase the selling value of the coffee shop. The findings showed that both exterior and interior elements significantly and positively influenced customers purchasing decisions.

Other findings by Sutiyo Wibowo & Bahrhun, 2024 on a coffee shops in Indonesia also mentions that store atmosphere has significant effect on the purchasing decision made by the audience. It shows that the emotional states brought by the store atmosphere, like the designs and services, triggers the interest to influence the purchase intention. This is further supported in the present study, in which the direct effect of Place Ambience confirms to have significant positive relationship to Purchase Intention ($\beta = 0.322$, $p < 0.001$). Therefore, the findings altogether highlight Place Ambience as the primary relational factor that drives customer's purchase intention.

6.3 The Effect of Anime Trend on Buyer Interest

Prior to previous study made by (Shi, 2024), it is mentioned that the use of anime IP is a very effective way of promotion, showing that the use of Anime Trend has a significant effect in affecting consumers in making a purchase. However, based on the research done for Indonesia's coffee shops audience in the present study, it is show that the effect of Anime Trend was statically insignificant towards the Buyer Interest ($\beta = 0.225$, $p = 0.120$). The disparity identified in this study may stem from targeting a broad consumer group rather than specifically focusing on consumers who are genuinely interest in the anime trend. Therefore, the anime trend may not serve as a primary mechanism through which buyer interest influences the coffee shop industry.

6.4 The Effect of Buyer Interest on Purchase Intention

The findings of the present study reveal that the Buyer Interest was significantly effective and has positive relationship towards Purchase Intention ($\beta = 0.615$, $p < 0.001$). This reinforces prior research by Wang et al., 2023, in which buyer's interest that was influenced by consumer perception toward the product. It's suggested that when consumers perceive something positively, their intention to buy also increases. Meaning that buyer interest drive purchase intention when it is effectively shapes the audience's perception and attitudes. Thus, buyer's interest plays a full mediating role in the relationship between the independent variables and dependent variables in the present research.

6.5 Limitations

Although the present study provides valuable insights, there's still several limitations that requires further investigation:

- a) **Specific Target Limitation:** Because this study relied on generalized consumer data, it wasn't able to fully capture the marketing impact of elements like Character Collaboration or the use of anime trends, which are seen to boost purchase intention within niche audiences.
- b) **Geographical Limitation:** Due to respondents taken only from the Jabodetabek, this research may not be fully generalizable due to a limited geographic area, hence it might not represent wider consumer behavior.
- c) **Targeted Big Coffee Shops:** The present study only focuses on the well-known coffee shop brands in Indonesia and therefore unable to fully capture the dynamics of smaller or less-established coffee shops. This resulting in the lack of a significant impact of character collaboration on purchase intention may be partly attributable to this limitation.

6.6 Managerial Insights

The present study contributes to the literature by integrating emotional and relational mechanisms. By focusing on the place ambience rather than character collaboration with anime trend on purchase intention, this study offers several managerial insights:

- 1) **Atmosphere comfort outweighs the use of trend:** Customer purchase interest is influenced more by store atmosphere rather than by the use of trends, as a comfortable and well-designed environment plays a crucial role in enhancing customer' ease and confidence when making purchasing decisions.
- 2) **Focus on building place ambience:** Since ambience significantly influences purchase intention, coffee shops in Indonesia are encouraged to focus on cultivating emotionally comforting environments to strengthen consumers' purchase intentions.
- 3) **The use of specific trends within a limited time period:** While trends can generate short-term engagement, their effectiveness may diminish over time, limiting their long-term strategic value.

7. Conclusions

Through the present study, it concludes that although character collaboration strategies aligned with anime trends have been adopted by several coffee shops in Indonesia, place ambience, particularly atmosphere and layout, plays a more central role in shaping purchase intention among Gen Z and Gen Y consumers. Buyer interest plays as a crucial mediating variable and fully mediates the relationship between place ambience and purchase intention. However, due to the respondents that were drawn from a general consumer population rather than a niche segment with a strong interest in anime, the effects of character collaboration may not have been effectively captured. Thus, the purchase intention of coffee shops in general is primarily driven by the shop's atmosphere and consumers' personal capabilities, rather than by the use of character collaboration and anime trends.

8. Recommendation

To fill in the gap and limitation of the present research, future research should focus more on the targeted respondents may reveal a significant influence of character collaboration and anime trends in enhancing purchase intention within the Indonesian coffee shop industry. In addition, expanding the scope of research to include a wider range of coffee shop brands across Indonesia may provide deeper insights into how promotional strategies can be better designed to enhance overall purchase intention.

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not applicable.

Informed Consent Statement: The following statement ensured the online consent of the respondents: "I have read the brief information about the research objectives and agree to participate in the survey."

Data Availability Statement: All data generated or analyzed during this present study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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